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GRA & DFA Approach for Optimum Material Selection of Aluminium Metal Matrix Composites: A Comparative Study

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Abstract

Objective: To draw the best combination of material parameters which gives optimized tensile strength, hardness and density properties of the aluminium metal matrix composite. **Methods:** In this study, three parameters (i.e., base material: Al5083, Al6082 and Al7075, reinforcement material: Fly-ash, SiC, and Al₂O₃, and percent of reinforcement material: 2.5%, 5% and 7.5%) were chosen, each with three levels, for the fabrication of AMMC samples in accordance with the Taguchi experimental design L₉ in order to evaluate the tensile strength, hardness and density properties. With the considered set of material combinations, the AMMC samples are fabricated by using stir casting process. **Findings:** The optimum material combinations are chosen to get optimized properties of AMMC samples using GRA & DFA approach. Since, grey relational analysis is one of the foremost techniques applied when the nature of information is incomplete and uncertain. The experimental results are analyzed using GRA & DFA and drawn the optimum combination of material parameter such as Al6082 (base material), SiC (reinforcement material) and 7.5% (per cent of reinforcement material) with GRA and Al6082 (base material), SiC (reinforcement material) and 5% (per cent of reinforcement material) with DFA to get optimized properties of AMMC sample. It also found that the confirmation experiment results are adequate. **Novelty:** The use of fly-ash reinforcement as secondary reinforcement has widely increased due to their low cost and easily available as waste in thermal power plants. From the experimental results, it is observed that the tensile strength, hardness and density properties of aluminium alloy samples are improved due to the addition of reinforcement materials using stir casting process.

Keywords: DFA & GRA approach; Stir casting process; AMMC samples; Composite properties: Ultimate Tensile Strength; Brinell hardness; and Density

1 Introduction

Metal Matrix Composites (MMCs) refer to metallic materials that have been strengthened through the incorporation of various metals, ceramics, or natural compounds. Metal Matrix Composites (MMCs) are fabricated through the dispersion of reinforcement materials within the matrix metal. The process of reinforcement is commonly employed with the aim of enhancing the inherent properties of the base metal, including but not limited to strength, stiffness, conductivity, and other relevant characteristics. Aluminium and its alloys have emerged as highly constructive materials for use as base metals in metal matrix composites due to their advantageous characteristics, including reduced weight, increased strength, exceptional thermal and electrical properties, cost efficiency, improved resistance to corrosion, and heightened damping capacity. The automotive, aerospace, and sports industries requires a variety of aluminum-composite components for use in diverse conditions⁽¹⁾. Consequently, extensive research has been conducted in recent years to investigate the combination of various aluminum alloys with different reinforcing elements⁽²⁻⁴⁾. The stability of the reinforcing elements at operating temperatures, as well as their non-reactivity, is important considerations⁽⁵⁾. Silicon Carbide (SiC) and Aluminium Oxide (Al₂O₃) are frequently employed as reinforcing agents. P. Chakrapani, T.S.A. Suryakumari concluded in their review of various researches as, Reinforcement particles play a significant role to alter the mechanical properties of AMMCs. Better results were obtained on tensile strength by using different reinforcement particles such as graphite, fly ash. Hardness of MMCs changes with the change in silicon carbide composition. Hardness of MMC increase with the addition of SiC weight fraction and Al₂O₃ weight fraction⁽⁶⁾. Additionally, there has been a growing trend in the use of fly-ash reinforcement, primarily due to its low cost and abundant availability as a waste product in thermal power plants⁽⁷⁾. The process of stir casting is a cost-effective method utilized for the production of aluminum based metal matrix composites⁽⁸⁾. On other hand, to achieve optimized combination of various parameters, extensive hundreds of trials have to be performed which costs high. The cost effective tool utilized for the optimization process is Design of Experiments (DoE), which involves the preparation of a series of tests to investigate the effects of specific changes in the input parameters of a system. This approach facilitates the aggregation of a substantial amount of resources and offers a meticulously structured strategy for addressing the research problem^(9,10). To explore the concept of multiple attributes decision-making, researchers often employ various techniques, including the Analytic Hierarchy Process (AHP)⁽¹¹⁾, data envelopment analysis (DEA), and grey relational analysis (GRA)⁽¹²⁾. Santonab Chakraborty proposed application of a newly developed multi-criteria decision-making tool, in the form of ordinal priority approach (OPA), for solving two parametric optimization problems for drilling operations of Al-MMCs⁽¹³⁾. One of the prominent techniques utilized in situations where information is incomplete and uncertain is grey relational analysis (GRA), which was introduced by Deng in 1989⁽¹⁴⁾. The authors^(15,16) have utilized a combined approach involving the Taguchi L₉ orthogonal array and the Grey Relational Analysis (GRA) technique to optimize the injection molding parameters. Using grey relational analysis (GRA). Jebarose Juliyaana, S et al.⁽¹⁷⁾ derived the optimal cutting parameters for addressing the best thrust force (TF), surface roughness (SR), and burr height (BH) of drilled holes for the composite LM5/ZrO₂. To validate the process output parameters, the Grey Relational Analysis (GRA) optimization approach was applied by Layatitdev Das et.al, and the effect of three process parameters, cutting speed, tool feed and cutting depth, is being studied on the machining responses⁽¹⁸⁾. A Taguchi coupled desirability function analysis was employed by S.V. Alagarsamy et.al,⁽¹⁹⁾ to determine the optimal parameters with an objective to maximize the material removal rate (MRR) and minimize the surface roughness (SR)

1.1 Research Gap

After studying the previous research, extensive research has been made on AMMCs and the machining of AMMCs. No researcher fabricated AMMCs by using the optimization technique for the selection of constituent parameters but randomly taking parameter levels, which may lead to a defective combination of constituent levels. In this issue, to fill the gap, this research has been proposed with the assistance of GRA (Gray Relational Analysis) and DFA (Desirability Function Analysis).

2 Methodology

The effective tools utilized for the optimization process is Grey Relational Analysis and Desirability Function Analysis coupled with Taguchi Design of Experiments (DoE), which involves the preparation of a series of tests to reduce the number of experiments and hence the cost of experimentation.

2.1 Process parameters and design of experiments

In order to produce the AMMC samples, the materials and their contribution are tabulated in Table 1, which was selected from past research. The experimental design for conducting the experiments was developed using the Taguchi orthogonal

array methodology, with the assistance of Mini-Tab software. The information presented in Table 2 provides a comprehensive overview of the material combinations utilized in the production of AMMC samples through the stir casting process.

Table 1. Parameters and their levels

Sl. No.	Parameters	Levels		
		1	2	3
1	Base material (BM)	Al5083	Al6082	Al7075
2	Reinforcement Material (RM)	FA	SiC	Al ₂ O ₃
3	Percentage of Reinforcement Material (PRM)	2.5%	5%	7.5

Table 2. L₉ orthogonal array design

AMMC Sample No.	Material Parameters		
	BM	RM	PRM
1	Al5083	FA	2.5
2	Al5083	SiC	5
3	Al5083	Al ₂ O ₃	7.5
4	Al6082	FA	5
5	Al6082	SiC	7.5
6	Al6082	Al ₂ O ₃	2.5
7	Al7075	FA	7.5
8	Al7075	SiC	2.5
9	Al7075	Al ₂ O ₃	5

2.2 Sample Fabrication

Firstly, the necessary amount of matrix material is introduced into the crucible, and the temperature is elevated to 850 °C and maintained at this level until the base material is completely melted. After complete melting of the matrix material, a 1% concentration of the wetting agent magnesium (Mg) is introduced into the molten metal. The reinforcement particles are gradually introduced into the molten matrix material while undergoing stirring (Figure 1), and this process is sustained for duration of five minutes. Subsequently, the heterogeneous slurry was introduced into distinct steel dies that had been preheated, facilitating the production of samples intended for subsequent testing. In accordance with the experimental design, the AMMC samples are prepared as depicted in Figure 2. Subsequently, these samples are subjected to machining processes in adherence to ASTM standards, as illustrated in Figure 3. The purpose of employing a wire-cut EDM machine is to preserve the inherent properties of the AMMC samples, thereby facilitating the subsequent evaluation of their tensile strength, hardness, and density.

Fig 1. Stir casting furnace

Fig 2. AMMC Sample with Die

Fig 3. AMMC test samples as per ASTM standards

The surface of the fabricated AMMC sample, was examined through the utilization of scanning electron microscopy (SEM), as illustrated in Figure 4. The observable phenomenon of reinforcement particle dispersion within the aluminum matrix material is evident. Hence, the stir casting process is a highly suitable technique for achieving a homogeneous dispersion of reinforcement particles within metal matrix composites. The incorporation of SiC particles into the aluminum matrix resulted in enhanced properties of the aluminum alloy. Similarly, the brittleness of the AMMC sample was also found to be heightened due to the agglomeration of SiC particles.

Fig 4. SEM image of fabricated AMMC sample

The prepared samples, in accordance with ASTM standards, undergo testing using a universal testing machine (Figure 5), a Brinell hardness tester (Figure 5), and a weighing method to evaluate their tensile strength, Brinell hardness number, and density. The obtained test results are organized in Table 3 and subsequently analyzed using gray relational analysis and Desirability Function Analysis.

Fig 5. Universal Testing Machine

Fig 6. Brinell Hardness Tester

2.3 Optimization using GRA

Grey Relational Analysis (GRA) employs a distinct notion of information. The concept delineates scenarios devoid of information as black while contrasting them with situations characterized by complete information as white. Nevertheless, it is important to note that both of these hypothetical scenarios are rarely encountered in practical applications. Indeed, circumstances that fall between these two extremes are commonly characterized as being ambiguous or indeterminate. Hence, a gray system refers to a system characterized by a combination of known and unknown information. According to this definition, the quantity and quality of information can be understood as existing on a spectrum ranging from a complete absence of information to a state of comprehensive information, represented metaphorically as a continuum from black to white with varying shades of gray in between. Given the inherent presence of uncertainty, individuals consistently find themselves positioned within an intermediate realm, situated between opposing extremes, and residing within a nuanced and ambiguous domain. The experimental results were analyzed using gray relational analysis in order to determine the optimal combination of material factors for achieving optimized ultimate tensile strength (UTS), Brinell hardness number (BHN), and density. The procedural steps for the same are provided below.

2.3.1 Data pre-processing

Data pre-processing, specifically data normalization, is typically necessary due to variations in range and unit among different data sequences. Different methodologies for data pre-processing in grey relational analysis are available depending on the characteristics of the data sequence.

If the target value of original sequence is infinite, then it has a characteristic of the “larger the better”. The original sequence can be normalized as follows:

$$x^*_i(k) = \frac{x^o_i(k) - \min x^o_i(k)}{\max x^o_i(k) - \min x^o_i(k)} \tag{1}$$

When the “smaller the better” is a characteristic of the original sequence, then the original sequence should be normalized as follows:

$$x^*_i(k) = \frac{\max x^o_i(k) - x^o_i(k)}{\max x^o_i(k) - \min x^o_i(k)} \tag{2}$$

However, if there is a definite target value “nominal the best” to be achieved, the original sequence will be normalized in form:

$$x^*_i(k) = 1 - \frac{|x^o_i(k) - x^o|}{\max x^o_i(k) - x^o} \tag{3}$$

Or, the original sequence can be simply normalized by the most basic methodology, i.e., let the values of original sequence are divided by the first value of the sequence:

$$x^*_i(k) = \frac{x^o_i(k)}{x^o_i(1)} \tag{4}$$

Where $i = 1 \dots, m$; $k = 1 \dots, n$. m is the number of experimental data items and n is the number of parameters. $x^o_i(k)$ Denotes the original sequence, $x^*_i(k)$ the sequence after the data pre-processing, $\max x^o_i(k)$ the largest value of $x^o_i(k)$, $\min x^o_i(k)$ the smallest value of $x^o_i(k)$, and x^o is the desired value.

2.3.2 Grey relational coefficient and grey relational grade

Grey relational analysis involves quantifying the degree of relevance between two systems or sequences, which is denoted as the Grey Relational Grade (GRG). Following the completion of data pre-processing, the grey relation coefficient $\xi_i(k)$ pertaining to the k^{th} performance characteristic in the i^{th} experiment can be mathematically represented as:

$$\xi_i(k) = \frac{\Delta_{\min} + \zeta \Delta_{\max}}{\Delta_{oi}(k) + \zeta \Delta_{\max}} \tag{5}$$

Where, Δ_{oi} is the Deviation sequence

$$\begin{aligned} \Delta_{oi} &= \|x^*_o(k) - x^*_i(k)\| \\ \Delta_{\min} &= \min_{\substack{j \in I \\ k \in K}} \|x^*_o(k) - x^*_j(k)\| \\ \Delta_{\max} &= \max_{\substack{j \in I \\ k \in K}} \|x^*_o(k) - x^*_j(k)\| \end{aligned} \tag{6}$$

$x^*_o(k)$ Denotes the reference sequence and $x^*_i(k)$ denotes the comparability sequence. ζ is distinguishing or identification coefficient: $\zeta [0, 1]$ (the value may be adjusted based on the actual system requirements). A value of ζ is the smaller and the distinguished ability is the larger. $\zeta = 0.5$ is generally used. After the Grey Relational Coefficient (GRC) is derived, it is usual to take the average value of the grey relational coefficients as the grey relational grade. The grey relational grade is defined as:

$$\gamma_i = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{k=1}^n \xi_i(k) \tag{7}$$

The grey relational grade γ_i represents the level of correlation between the reference sequence and the comparability sequence. If the two sequences are identical, then the value of grey relational grade is equal to 1.

2.4 Optimization using desirability functional analysis

After analysing with GRA the experimental results were also analysed by using Desirability Function analysis(DFA), in order to determine the optimal combination of material factors for achieving optimized ultimate tensile strength (UTS), Brinell hardness number (BHN) and Density. The following are the steps for DFA.

2.4.1 Calculate the individual desirability (d_i)

For the corresponding responses using the formula proposed by Derringer and Suich. There are three forms of the desirability functions according to the response characteristics.

(a) **The nominal-the-best:** The value of \hat{y} is required to achieve a particular target T, the desirability function can be written as

$$d_i = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{\hat{y} - y_{min}}{T - y_{min}}\right)^s, & y_{min} \leq y \leq T, \quad s \geq 0 \\ \left(\frac{\hat{y} - y_{min}}{T - y_{min}}\right)^t, & T \leq \hat{y} \leq y_{min}, \quad t \geq 0 \\ 0 & \end{cases} \tag{8}$$

Where the y_{max} and y_{min} represent the upper and lower tolerance limits of \hat{y} and s and t represent the indices.

(b) **The larger-the-better:** The value of \hat{y} is expected to be the larger the better. The desirability function can be written as

$$d_i = \begin{cases} 0, & \hat{y} \leq y_{min} \\ \left(\frac{\hat{y} - y_{min}}{y_{max} - y_{min}}\right)^r, & y_{min} \leq \hat{y} \leq y_{max}, \quad r \geq 0 \\ 1, & \hat{y} \geq y_{max} \end{cases} \tag{9}$$

Where the y_{min} represents the lower tolerance limit of \hat{y} , the y_{max} represents the upper tolerance limit of \hat{y} and r represents index.

(c) **The smaller-the-better:** The value of \hat{y} is expected to be the smaller the better, the desirability function can be written as

$$d_i = \begin{cases} 1, & \hat{y} \leq y_{min} \\ \left(\frac{\hat{y} - y_{max}}{y_{min} - y_{max}}\right)^r, & y_{min} \leq \hat{y} \leq y_{max}, \quad r \geq 0 \\ 0, & \hat{y} \geq y_{min} \end{cases} \tag{10}$$

Where the y_{min} represents the lower tolerance limit of \hat{y} , the y_{max} represents the upper tolerance limit of \hat{y} and r represents the weight. The s, t and r indicate the weights and are defined according to the requirement of the user.

2.4.2 Calculate the overall desirability (D)

The individual desirability values have been accumulated to calculate the overall desirability, using the following equation.

$$D = (d_1 * d_2 * d_2 \dots \dots \dots d_n)^{1/n} \tag{11}$$

Here D is the overall or composite desirability value, d_i is the individual desirability value of i^{th} quality characteristic and n is the total number of responses.

3 Results and Discussion

The test results presented in Table 3 are utilized to assess the optimal mechanical and physical properties of AMMC through the application of the GRA approach. In the GRA approach, the initial step involves normalizing the experimental results through the utilization of equations in the data pre-processing stage, specifically from Equations (1), (2), (3) and (4). The utilization of Equations (1) and (2) is crucial in achieving optimal outcomes as they are employed to standardize the properties of tensile strength, hardness, and density. Typically, manufacturers prioritize materials with high tensile strength, high hardness, and low density. In order to meet the current demands of manufacturers, the experimental values, specifically tensile and hardness values, are normalized using Equation (1), while density values are normalized using Equation (2). The tabulated values in Table 4 represent the normalized values.

Table 3. Experimental Results

Exp. No	Experimental Results		
	Ultimate tensile strength (N/mm ²)	Brinell Hardness Number (BHN)	Density (D)Kg/m ³
1	115	55.84	2786.40
2	136	67.47	2816.90

Continued on next page

Table 3 continued

3	138	69.21	3097.30
4	131	63.11	2855.10
5	155	72.4	3007.50
6	125	58.34	2742.40
7	142	70.23	3132.30
8	129	60.73	2727.27
9	134	63.88	2828.30

The deviation sequence is evaluated from the normalized values by employing Equation (6) to determine the grey relation coefficient and grey relation grade values, after the experimental values have been normalized with respect to their characteristics. The GRC and GRG values are determined through the utilization of Equations (5) and (7). All of these values are dimensionless results obtained by normalizing the experimental results, and they are evaluated with respect to their respective characteristics. The tabulation of the deviation sequence (Delta), GRC, and GRG values can be found in Table 4.

Table 4. NEVs, DVNEVs, GRCs and Grey Relational Grade

Sl. No	Normalized experimental values			Delta values of NEV			Grey Relational Coefficients			Grey Relational Grade (GRG)
	UTS	BHN	D	UTS	BHN	D	UTS	BHN	D	
1	0	0.1	0.8540	1.000	1.0000	0.1460	0.3333	0.3333	0.7740	0.4802
2	0.525	0.7023	0.7787	0.475	0.2977	0.2213	0.5128	0.6268	0.6932	0.6109
3	0.575	0.8074	0.0864	0.425	0.1926	0.9136	0.5405	0.7219	0.3537	0.5387
4	0.400	0.4390	0.6844	0.600	0.5610	0.3156	0.4545	0.4713	0.6130	0.5129
5	1.000	1.0000	0.3081	0.000	0.0000	0.6919	1.0000	1.0000	0.4195	0.8065
6	0.250	0.1510	0.9626	0.750	0.8490	0.0374	0.4000	0.3706	0.9305	0.5670
7	0.675	0.8690	0.0000	0.325	0.1310	1.0000	0.6061	0.7923	0.3333	0.5772
8	0.350	0.2953	1.0000	0.650	0.7047	0.0000	0.4348	0.4150	1.0000	0.6166
9	0.475	0.4855	0.7506	0.525	0.5145	0.2494	0.4878	0.4929	0.6672	0.5493

After normalizing the experimental values with respect their characteristics, deviation sequence is assessed from the normalized values by using Equation (6) for grey relation coefficient and grey relation grade values. The GRC and GRG values are calculated by using the Equations (5) and (7). All these values are dimensionless results from normalized to grey relational grade values but are with respect their characteristics. The deviation sequence (Delta), GRC and GRG values are tabulated in Table 4.

Table 5. Grey relational grade values for each factor at each level

Level	BM	RM	PRM
1	0.5433	0.5234	0.5546
2	0.6288	0.6780	0.5577
3	0.5810	0.5517	0.6408
Delta	0.0855	0.1546	0.0862
Rank	3	1	2

Upon completion of the grey relational coefficient calculations for each response, the grey relational grade is subsequently determined for each factor at every level. This process enables the identification of the optimal level for each factor by considering their respective grey relational grade values. In the Grey Relational Analysis (GRA) approach, it is observed that the influential factor with the highest grey relational grade value among its considered levels represents the optimum level. The material factors are assessed and ranked based on their delta values in order to determine the most influential factor in achieving optimal properties. The ranking and mean values are presented in Table 5 and Figure 7, respectively.

From the Figure 7 and Table 5, it is observed the optimum material combination for getting the optimal properties in aluminium metal matrix composites through GRA are:

- Base Material at 3rd Level i.e., Al 6082
- Reinforcement Material is at 2nd Level i.e., SiC
- Percentage of reinforcement Material is at Level 3 i.e., 7.5%

Fig 7. Grey relational grade values for each factor at each level

In the DFA approach the individual desirability values using equation 9 for UTS and BHN and Equation (10) for Density Composite Desirability values are calculated using Equation (10). Also, composite desirability values are calculated using Equation (11) and tabulated the values in the Table 6.

Table 6. Individual desirability values

Sl No	Individual desirability values (d _i)			Composite desirability values (D _c)
	UTS	BHN	D	
1	0.000	0.0000	0.8540	0.0000
2	0.525	0.7023	0.7787	0.6597
3	0.575	0.8074	0.0864	0.3423
4	0.400	0.4390	0.6844	0.4935
5	1.000	1.0000	0.3081	0.6754
6	0.250	0.1510	0.9626	0.3312
7	0.675	0.8690	0.0000	0.0000
8	0.350	0.2953	1.0000	0.4693
9	0.475	0.4855	0.7506	0.5573

After that the composite desirability values are calculated for each factor at each level (Table 7 & Figure 8) and the optimal level for each factor is identified based on their individual composite desirability values. The optimal level of any influential factor has the highest composite desirability value among their considered levels.

Table 7. Composite desirability values for each factor at each level

Level	BM	RM	PRM
1	0.3340	0.1645	0.2668
2	0.5000	0.6015	0.5702
3	0.3422	0.4103	0.3392
Delta	0.1660	0.4370	0.3033
Rank	3	1	2

From the Figure 8 and Table 7, it is observed the optimum material combination for getting the optimal properties in aluminium metal matrix composites through DFA are:

- Base Material at 3rd Level i.e., Al 6082
- Reinforcement Material is at 2nd Level i.e., SiC
- Percentage of reinforcement Material is at Level 3 i.e., 5%

Confirmation Experiment

Fig 8. Composite desirability values for each factor at each level

Using the aforementioned combination of materials, the AMMC sample was manufactured and subsequently subjected to testing in order to validate the obtained results. Based on the data presented in Table 8, it can be observed that the results of GRA are better than that of DFA.

Table 8. Confirmation test Results

GRA				DFA			
Optimum material combination	UTS	BHN	D	Optimum material combination	UTS	BHN	D
Al6082/7.5% SiC MMC	155	72.4	3007	Al6082/5% SiC MMC	147	69	3002

4 Conclusions

Based on the findings of this study, the following conclusions have been derived:

1. It can be inferred that the stir casting process is a highly suitable method for the production of aluminum metal matrix composite samples, and the incorporation of SiC particles leads to an enhancement in the properties of the aluminum alloy. The incorporation of SiC particles leads to an increase in the density of the aluminum alloy. Hence, it is recognized that the selection of optimal casting parameters is crucial to achieving a consistent and even distribution of reinforcement materials.
2. Based on the GRA analysis, it can be concluded that the combination of Al6082, SiC, and 7.5% material is determined to be the optimal combination for enhancing the properties of the aluminum alloy. And the hardness value and tensile strength of an aluminum alloy are increased due to the agglomeration of SiC particles.
3. Based on the DFA analysis, it can be concluded that the combination of Al6082, SiC, and 5% material is determined to be the optimal combination for enhancing the properties of the aluminum alloy. And the hardness value and tensile strength of an aluminum alloy are increased due to the agglomeration of SiC particles.
4. The confirmation experiment demonstrates that the GRA is effective when compared to DFA while addressing these specific research problems.
5. It can be concluded that the research gap has been filled by using the concept of taguchi-coupled GRA and DFA effectively by reducing the number of experiments.

5 Future scope of work

Several optimization techniques, such as denga, vikor, and fuzzy logic, can be used to achieve a better combination of constituents for fabricating AMMCs.

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